

LCA of a Critical Raw Material (CRM): State-of-Art of Cobalt Production

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cobalt (Co) is a pivotal CRM for multiple applications (Figure 1), and a key-enabler for the energy transition. Its demand is expected to grow 10-20 times by 2030, compared to 2014 values (Deetman *et al.*, 2018), amplifying concerns about the social and environmental impacts of its production.

Co is almost entirely obtained as a by-product of Cu (60%) and Ni (38%). It is mainly extracted in the DRC and in Indonesia, while its refining to metal or battery chemicals principally occurs in China (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Cobalt market

Figure 2: Geographical distribution of the Co supply chain

3. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

In general, available LCAs of Co chemicals (Figure 3) exhibit limited geographical representativeness, as they assess production routes that do not represent a significant share of global cobalt production, excluding the work of Dai *et al.* (2018). Furthermore, despite the efforts undertaken by the mining industry to harmonize the LCAs of metals, studies often adopt different methodological approaches, particularly regarding allocation (see Table 1). Being cobalt a co-product of different metals, this choice affects the results and hinders the comparability among studies.

Moreover, being refining operations responsible for a great share of the environmental impacts of cobalt chemicals, the LCA results are highly affected by the refining location, and consequent electricity grid mix, considered.

While advocating for a more comprehensive LCA of Co compounds, comparisons of future emerging Co production routes should preferably use as benchmarks for current global Co production the works by Dai *et al.* (2018) and by the Cobalt Institute (2019); these studies represent cobalt refining in China and global production outside of China, respectively, providing a comprehensive basis for comparison.

2. METHODOLOGY

LCA is a standardised (ISO 14000 series) methodology that can be used to evaluate the potential environmental impacts of the production of Co compounds. In view of the emerging future regulations (e.g., battery regulation), harmonized and representative LCA of battery metals are required.

Here, a systematic review of the literature on LCAs of cobalt products was conducted by combining studies found in literature alongside datasets from prominent LCA databases (e.g. Ecoinvent). The goals of this literature review were to:

- identify the methodological approaches adopted by LCAs practitioners and guidelines for conducting LCAs of cobalt products;
- compare impact estimations from different sources, pointing out how different production routes, refinery locations, as well as methodological choices, can affect the environmental impact assessment of cobalt production;
- define benchmarks to enable future comparison of current cobalt production routes with novel emerging ones.

Figure 3: LCIA results for CoSO₄ production

Table 1: Data sources

Reference	Deposit type	Geographical coverage	Allocation
Cobalt Institute (2019)	Multiple processing routes analysed	Global, excluding China (no Chinese refineries included)	M
Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Ni-Cu-Co	China	M
Crenna <i>et al.</i> (2021) based on Dai <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Cu-Co	DRC (mining & beneficiation) China (refining)	M & E
Bollwein <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Ni-Cu-Co	Canada (mining & beneficiation) Norway (refining)	E
Rinne <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Au-Co (future potential deposit)	Finland	E
Ecoinvent v3.9.1 (2023) based on Cobalt Institute (2015)	Multiple processing routes analysed	Global (mining & beneficiation) China (refining)	E

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